

Article

Indonesia's Economic Growth: Role of Human Capital, Physical Capital, and Social Infrastructure

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Abstract: *Indonesia's economic prosperity is measured by its growth, a key United Nations Sustainable Development Goal (SDG 8). Despite funding increases, education and healthcare gaps impede workforce development and economic progress. Inadequate social infrastructure reduces production efficiency. Limited research exists on the impact of human capital, physical capital, and social infrastructure on Indonesia's growth. This research examines these factors and technological progress on GDP using an endogenous growth framework. The study examines physical capital's contribution, assesses human capital's impact, analyzes social infrastructure's effect, and explores their interplay in growth. It analyzed 54 years of data from 1970 to 2023, focusing on GDP per capita, physical capital, labor, human capital, technological progress, and social infrastructure. Data came from World Bank Development Indicators and Penn World Table 10.1. Researchers converted data to logarithmic scales and analyzed them using EViews 12. Ordinary least squares estimation examined macroeconomic indicators. Augmented Dickey-Fuller and Philips-Perron tests checked variable stationarity. Johansen cointegration results showed cointegration between variables, with lag order 2 as optimal. Findings revealed that physical capital, labor, and human capital positively affected output, while social infrastructure negatively impacted output due to resource misallocation. Technological advancement has no effect. The Theil coefficient of 0.003355 indicated outstanding performance, while SMAPE showed 49.35% average prediction error. The study concluded that capital, labor, human capital, and social infrastructure influence growth. Addressing corruption, disparities, and infrastructure gaps between rural and urban regions is essential. Implementing governance reform, fair investment, innovative financing, and community involvement will help realize the social infrastructure's potential for growth.*

Keywords: *Economic growth; human capital; physical capital; technology; social infrastructure*

1. Introduction

Economic growth serves as a primary measure of a nation's welfare and is one of the main goals of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDG 8). Within economic studies, the endogenous growth model highlights the significance of internal factors, such as human capital and social

infrastructure development, in boosting Gross Domestic Product (GDP). However, human capital, encompassing education levels, workforce skills, training, and health, is widely acknowledged as a crucial element in driving economic productivity and fostering innovation (Ali et al., 2018). At the same time, social infrastructure, including healthcare services, education, and robust social institutions, fosters an environment that enhances economic efficiency (Singh, 2022).

Agricultural Economists have long been concerned about income disparities across nations. The endogenous growth model is valuable for understanding this issue, emphasizing internal factors in sustainable economic growth. Two key components are human capital and social infrastructure. Human capital, including skills, knowledge, and health of the labor force, directly boosts economic productivity and innovation. On the other hand, social infrastructure, such as education, healthcare, and effective governance, fosters an environment supporting human capital development and investment. Empirical research consistently shows the beneficial effect of human capital on economic growth. According to Yuhan (2024), a nation's initial level of education is positively linked to its future economic growth, as education can enhance overall productivity.

Mankiw et al. (1992) expanded the Solow model by adding human capital, demonstrating that the model could account for most of the differences in income across countries. Wang & Liu (2016) research indicates that the caliber of education, as reflected in standardized test results, significantly influences economic development. Besides human capital, social infrastructure is also crucial for economic progress. Högström et al. (2022) assert that robust institutions, such as the enforcement of legal frameworks and the safeguarding of property rights, are essential for enduring economic development. Enneking et al. (2024) discovered that nations with superior institutions generally experience more rapid growth. Timilsina et al. (2024) demonstrate that public health plays a crucial role in boosting economic growth. When it comes to assessing and contrasting GDP across nations, Feenstra et al. (2015) underscore the significance of differentiating between GDP calculated from the expenditure perspective and that from the production perspective.

GDP from the expenditure side indicates the standard of living, whereas GDP from the production side assesses a nation's productive capacity. Additionally, they stress employing constant prices across countries and over time to achieve precise GDP comparisons. Economic growth benefits from human capital, especially when bolstered by economic opportunities and robust legal institutions (Ali et al., 2018). Research utilizing panel data methods indicates that the impact of human capital on GDP becomes more pronounced when it is integrated with other societal elements, such as social infrastructure and economic opportunities (Wulandari et al., 2021). Social infrastructure contributes to boosting the effectiveness of both physical capital and human resources, which in turn speeds up economic development (Chou, 2006).

In Indonesia, the last twenty years have seen a positive trend in investments in human capital and social infrastructure, yet the country still grapples with insignificant economic growth challenges. Indonesia's Human Development Index (HDI) has risen from 61.53 in 2005 to 72.99 in 2022 (BPS), driven by enhancements in life expectancy, average schooling years, and adjusted per capita spending. For Indonesians aged 25 and older, the Average Length of Schooling (RLS) increased from 7.65 years in 2010 to 8.69 years in 2023 (BPS). Over the past two decades, the School Participation Rate (APS) across all educational levels has improved, although disparities between urban and rural areas persist. The success of human capital is heavily influenced by physical capital (Amir-ud-din et al., 2019). Hardianti et al. (2020) highlighted that the development of economic infrastructure, such as roads and electricity, alongside social infrastructure like education and healthcare, collectively influences the advancement of economic growth. The government has undertaken significant investments in infrastructure projects, including the construction of toll roads, airports, ports, and power plants. These infrastructure upgrades are projected to enhance connectivity, decrease transportation costs, and attract investments, thereby improving the quality of human capital and increasing productivity (Garzarelli & Limam, 2019).

Despite the rise in government funding for education and healthcare, challenges such as unequal access and varying service quality continue to hinder the development of a skilled and innovative workforce (Nugroho et al., 2022). Conversely, inadequate social infrastructure impedes economic development by

raising transaction costs and diminishing the efficiency of the labor market (Singh, 2022). This research examines how human capital and social infrastructure affect Indonesia's GDP within an endogenous growth framework. The model explains income differences among countries by considering these factors as GDP components. Understanding these elements can help develop policies to accelerate growth, convergence, and reduce inequalities. The findings can guide Indonesian policymakers in enhancing workforce quality and social infrastructure.

A study conducted by Paksi (2020) investigated the determinants of economic growth in Indonesia, utilizing time series data from 1991 to 2019 and employing the OLS method for analysis. The results revealed that household growth, export growth, and inflation significantly influence the nation's economic development. In a separate study, Agusalim et al. (2022) analyzed whether Indonesia's economy is predominantly driven by physical or human capital. This research utilized secondary data, including time-series data from 2010 to 2018 and cross-sectional data from 33 Indonesian provinces, analyzed through panel ordinary least squares, random effects, and fixed effects. The findings suggest that physical capital has a greater impact on Indonesia's economy than human capital. Within the realm of human capital, health is a critical factor in promoting economic growth, whereas education does not significantly affect economic growth. Widarni & Bawono (2021) explored the influence of human capital and technology on Indonesia's economic advancement using 35 years of time series data and the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) approach for analysis. Their findings indicate that improving human capital through education contributes to economic growth, and technology positively affects economic growth. Human resources and technology are essential components for economic growth in Indonesia. Pratama & Taufiq (2023) investigated the impact of economic and social infrastructure on economic growth in East Java from 2008 to 2022, using ordinary least squares for their analysis. The study considered variables such as economic growth, electricity infrastructure, road infrastructure, health infrastructure, and education infrastructure. The results showed that infrastructure related to electricity, health, and education positively and significantly impacts economic growth, while road infrastructure does not have an effect.

Recent studies on the factors influencing Indonesia's economic growth frequently examine human capital, physical capital, technological progress, or social infrastructure in isolation. Alternatively, they focus on specific elements, such as comparing physical and human capital or analyzing particular infrastructure types. There is a lack of comprehensive analysis that simultaneously considers human capital, physical capital, and social infrastructure to evaluate their combined and individual effects on Indonesia's economic growth. Although the positive impact of technology on economic growth is recognized, its interaction with human capital and infrastructure investments in Indonesia requires further exploration to guide policies aimed at innovation-driven growth. Therefore, this study assessed the impact of human capital, physical capital, and social infrastructure on Indonesia's economic growth, with technological progress acting as a mediating factor, providing valuable insights for developing sustainable development policies. The research aims to evaluate and measure the roles of human capital, physical capital, and social infrastructure in driving Indonesia's economic progress. The specific objectives of the study include evaluating the impact of physical and human capital on the nation's economic development and examining the role of social infrastructure in advancing the country's economy.

The study proposes the following hypotheses: H1: Human and physical capital significantly and positively affect Indonesia's economic growth. H2: Social infrastructure has a negative influence on Indonesia's economic growth.

2. Materials and Methods

This study adopted a quantitative methodology, systematically using numerical data and applying statistical techniques to investigate the connection between Indonesia's economic growth and macroeconomic variables (Midamba et al., 2025). This study analyzed 54 years of annual time series data from 1970 to 2023. We focus on real GDP per capita (Y), physical capital (K), labor (L), human capital (HK), technological progress (T), and social infrastructure (SI). The dataset is sourced from the World Bank Development Indicators (WDI) and Penn World Table version 10.1 (PWT). To enhance

model validity and economic interpretability, the researchers converted the data into logarithmic scales and analyzed them using EViews version 12 software.

2.1. Theoretical Model for Economic Growth

This study utilizes an expanded version of the augmented Solow growth model (Mankiw et al., 1992), which builds upon the classic neoclassical Solow model by adding human capital as an extra component in the aggregate production function. The production function is defined as follows:

$$Y(t) = K(t)^\alpha H(t)^\beta [(A(t)L(t))^{1-\alpha-\beta}] \quad (1)$$

where:

$Y(t)$ = Output (GDP) at time t

$K(t)$ = Physical capital

$H(t)$ = Human capital

$A(t)$ = Level of technology

$L(t)$ = Labor force

α and β are output elasticities of physical and human capital, respectively.

To further enrich the model, we consider technological progress and social infrastructure as determinants of total factor productivity (A), drawing on endogenous growth theory. Thus, TFP is modeled as:

$$A(t) = A_0 e^{\delta T(t) + \gamma S(t)} \quad (2)$$

where:

$T(t)$ = Technological progress (e.g., R&D investment, innovation index)

$SI(t)$ = Social infrastructure (e.g., institutional quality, governance, public infrastructure)

δ and γ are elasticities capturing the impact of technology and social infrastructure.

This integrated approach allows us to maintain the empirical tractability and convergence properties of the Solow framework. Equation 3 represents the Ordinary Least Squares estimation model, incorporating both the augmented Solow growth model and the endogenous model.

$$\ln Y_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \ln K_t + \beta_2 \ln L_t + \beta_3 \ln HK_t + \beta_4 \ln T_t + \beta_5 \ln SI_t + \varepsilon_t \quad (3)$$

where:

β_0 is the Intercept or constant

$\beta_1 - \beta_5$: Coefficient of the explanatory variables

ε_t : Error term.

2.2. Econometric Model Specification

2.2.1. Unit Root Test

In this study, unit root tests were conducted to assess the stationarity of economic variables, ensuring their appropriateness for policymaking and avoiding unit root problems by employing the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (Dickey & Fuller, 1979) and (Philips & Perron, 1988) tests. The ADF unit equation is represented in the form (equations 4 and 5):

$$\Delta z_t = \delta_0 + \delta_1 z_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^k \alpha_i \Delta z_{t-i} + \mu_t \quad (4)$$

$$\Delta z_t = \delta_0 + \delta_1 t + \delta_2 Z_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^k \alpha_i \Delta Z_{t-i} + \mu_t \tag{5}$$

The ADF regression tests the presence of the unit root of Z_t where t and k mean the time and number of lags included in the unit root testing regression. The ΔZ_{t-1} denotes the first difference of the variable with k lags. The term μ_t adjusts the errors of autocorrelation, while α_i , δ_0 , δ_1 , and δ_2 are estimated parameters. After unit root tests, determining the optimal lag order for variables is crucial for efficient, unbiased estimates. Lag selection relies on information criteria, influenced by sample size, and involves choosing the lag with the smallest criterion value for the estimated model.

2.2.2. Cointegration test

The Johansen cointegration technique was employed to identify the number of cointegration vectors in an unrestricted vector autoregression model. Equation 6 illustrates the Johansen cointegration formula used in this context.

$$\Delta X_t = \beta_1 + \beta_2 T + \Pi X_{t-1} + \sum_{k=1}^{m-1} \Gamma_k \Delta X_{t-k} + \Phi D_t + \varepsilon_t \tag{6}$$

In a system where $\pi = \sum_{k=1}^m A_k = I$ and $\Gamma_k = -\sum_{l=k+1}^m A_l$, X_t is a $(X \times 1)$ is a dimensional vector representing variables and $I(1)$, Π , Γ_k & Φ are parameter matrices to be estimated, D_t is a vector containing deterministic components, and ε_t is a random error term with a zero mean and constant variance. There are two methods of testing for the reduced rank (Π), the trace test and the maximum eigenvalue specified in equations (7) and (8).

$$\lambda_{trace} = -T \sum_{i=r+1}^q \ln(1 - \lambda_i^2) \tag{7}$$

$$\lambda_{max}(r, r + 1) = -T \ln(1 - \lambda_{r+1}) \tag{8}$$

Where λ_i is the estimated ordered eigenvalue derived from the estimated matrix, and T represents the number of observations after accounting for lag adjustments. The trace statistic evaluates the null hypothesis that the number of unique cointegration vectors is at most r , compared to a broader alternative. Meanwhile, the maximum eigenvalue test examines the null hypothesis that there are cointegrating vectors against the alternative hypothesis of having $r + 1$ cointegrating vectors.

Table 1. Description and measurements of macroeconomic variables

Variable	Description	Measurement unit	Data source	Expected effects
Dependent variable				
Y	Real GDP per capita	Constant 2015 (US\$)	WDI	
Independent variables				
K	Capital stock at current PPPs	Millions 2017 US\$	Penn World Table version 10.01	+
L	Labor	Number of persons engaged in millions	Penn World Table version 10.01	+
HK	Human capital index	Based on years of schooling and returns to education	Penn World Table version 10.01	+
T	Technological progress	Number of patents, residents	WDI	+
SI	Social infrastructure	People using at least basic drinking water services (% of population)	WDI	+/-

Source: Author’s computation (2025)

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Descriptive Statistics

Table 2 presents the descriptive statistics for Indonesia's output, physical capital, labor, human capital, technological progress, and social infrastructure, based on 54 observations spanning from 1970 to 2023.

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics

	Y	K	L	HK	T	SI
Mean	20,780,149	4,986,165	82.22	1.833	392.63	78.35
Maximum	40,181,953	17,715,404	131	2	3,093	95.23
Minimum	8,354,363	309,822	34	1	1	70
Std. Deviation	10,319,149	6,246,133	31.17	0.38	631.45	7.67
Skewness	0.60	1.11	-0.01	-1.79	2.33	0.84
Kurtosis	2.16	2.53	1.77	4.20	8.69	2.25
Jarque-Bera	4.84	11.56	3.40	32.04	121.57	7.58
Probability	0.0891	0.0031	0.1823	0.0000	0.0000	0.0225
Observations	54	54	54	54	54	54

Source: Author's computation (2025)

The results in Table 2 show Indonesia's real GDP per capita averaged US \$20,780,149, with a standard deviation of US \$10,319,149 during the studied period. Physical capital averaged US\$ 4,986,165 with a standard deviation of US\$ 6,246,133. The labor force averaged 82.22 million, with a standard deviation of 31.17 million, while human capital averaged 1.83, with a standard deviation of 0.38. Technological progress averaged 392.63, with a standard deviation of 623.45 applications, and social infrastructure averaged 78.35%, with a standard deviation of 7.67%. Most macroeconomic indicators were skewed to the right, whereas labor and human capital were skewed to the left. All kurtosis values were positive, indicating a more peaked distribution. The Jarque-Bera test results showed that output, physical capital, human capital, technological progress, and social infrastructure had probability values below the 5% threshold, suggesting these indicators are not normally distributed. Only labor had a probability value exceeding 5%, indicating normal distribution.

3.2. Correlation Matrix Results

A correlation matrix displays relationships between economic variables in a study, presenting correlations for every possible value pair in a tabular format. Table 3 displays the results of the correlation matrix for output, physical capital, labor, human capital, technological progress, and social infrastructure in Indonesia.

Table 3. Correlation matrix results

	Y	K	L	HK	T	SI
Y	1					
K	0.94	1				
L	0.97	0.94	1			
HK	0.71	0.56	0.72	1		
T	-0.16	-0.16	-0.20	-0.29	1	
SI	0.83	0.71	0.87	0.91	-0.27	1

Source: Author's computation (2025)

The correlation matrix in Table 3 shows a significant positive correlation between physical capital, labor, human capital, and social infrastructure with output, while technological progress has a weak negative correlation. This supports classical theory, indicating that physical capital boosts production capacity, labor enhances productivity, and social infrastructure creates stable economic conditions. The weak negative correlation of technological progress with output may result from disruptive technologies temporarily lowering productivity during implementation. Traditional industries may be slow to adopt new technologies. Labor, human capital, and social infrastructure strongly correlate with physical

capital, while technological progress is weakly negatively correlated. Discrepancies between human skills and new technology demands can hinder advancement. Human capital and social infrastructure have a strong positive connection with labor, unlike technological progress. Strong institutions are vital for education systems, while social infrastructure supports skill-driven economic activities that enhance productivity. Social infrastructure is strongly linked to human capital and weakly negatively correlated with technological progress. Regulatory obstacles might impede technology adoption, even with high-quality infrastructure.

3.3. Stationary Unit Roots Tests

A unit root test determines if a time series variable is non-stationary and contains a unit root. The null hypothesis asserts a unit root, while the alternative suggests the variable is stationary, trend stationary, or explosive, depending on the test. The study employed Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) and Phillips-Perron (PP) unit root tests, which are essential tools for assessing the integration order (stationarity) of macroeconomic variables. This is crucial because non-stationary data can result in misleading spurious outcomes. The following is a detailed summary of these tests, their applications, and the interpretation of results as presented in Table 4.

Table 4. Unit Root Test results

Variables	ADF		PP		Order of integration
	Levels	1 st Differences	Levels	1 st Differences	
lnY	-5.411072***	-5.227560***	-4.953906***	-5.159483***	I (0)
ln K	-1.981453	-3.207508*	-1.782404	-2.185668	I (1)
ln L	-0.972842	-5.128173***	-1.177410	-5.125665***	I (1)
ln HK	-2.567012	-5.393768***	-2.767835	-5.21234***	I (1)
ln T	-7.555685***	-12.12357***	-7.652647***	-50.40321***	I (0)
ln SI	-3.515523***	-5.661759***	-1.430582	-7.505480***	I (0)

Source: Author's computation (2025)

The findings show output, technological advancement, and social infrastructure are stationary at I(0), while physical capital, labor, and human capital are stationary at I(1). I(0) for output indicates a deterministic trend, implying stable economic growth. This aligns with research like Nepal's GDP analysis, demonstrating cointegration at levels after considering trends (Koirala, 2009). Technological progress might be better understood through growth rates, such as R&D efficiency improvements. For instance, log-transformed Germany's CPI and M3 were stationary at I(0) (EI-Abed & Zardoub, 2019). Social infrastructure often returns to its average state, especially when analyzing enduring institutions and economic results (Koirala, 2009; Kusu & Chen, 2017). First difference stationarity in physical capital suggests ongoing capital accumulation, like machinery, necessitating a differencing model for growth rates (Humpe & McMillan, 2020). Labor forces and human capital frequently exhibit stochastic trends due to population growth and skill development. Nepal's labor data needed differencing for stationarity (Koirala, 2009).

3.4. Lag Order Selection Criteria

Once series integration has been assessed, the next step is to determine the correct lag order for macroeconomic variables in OLS estimation. The research adopted the optimal lag order of the vector autoregressive (VAR) model, using LogL, likelihood ratio (LR) statistic, final predictor error (FPE), Akaike information criterion (AIC), Schwarz information criterion (SC), and Hannan-Quinn information criterion (HQ). The findings are summarized in Table 5.

Table 5. Lag order selection criteria

Lag	LogL	LR	FPE	AIC	SC	HQ
0	-303.05	NA	0.005853	11.89	12.11	11.97
1	133.55	755.65	1.320e-09	-3.52	-1.95	-2.92
2	258.32	187.15*	4.18e-11*	-6.94*	-4.01*	-5.81*

Source: Author’s computation (2025)

Table 5 shows that the second lag order outperforms the first, with lower values for all five criteria: LR (187.15), FPE (4.18e-11), AIC (-6.94), SC (-4.01), and HQ (-5.81). These results indicate that lag order 2 is superior to lag order 1 when evaluated using the LR, FPE, AIC, SC, and HQ metrics. Thus, the model with lag order 2 offers greater efficiency and a more accurate data representation than the model with lag order 1.

3.5. Johansen Cointegration Results

The research examines long-term relationships among macroeconomic factors like physical capital, labor, human capital, technological advancement, and social infrastructure concerning economic growth using cointegration methods. Table 6 shows estimated outcomes using the Trace and Max-eigen statistic methods. Trace and Max-eigenvalue test indicates 4 cointegrating eqn (s) at the 0.05 level; * denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level; *MacKinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) p-values.

Table 6. Cointegration results

Hypothesized No. of CE (s)	Eigenvalue	Trace statistic	0.05 Critical value	p-value	Max-eigen statistic	0.05 critical value	p-value
None*	0.692	158.488	95.754	0.0000	61.218	40.078	0.0001
At most 1*	0.509	97.269	69.819	0.0001	37.039	33.877	0.0203
At most 2*	0.420	60.231	47.856	0.0023	28.343	27.584	0.0399
At most 3*	0.323	31.888	29.797	0.0283	20.256	21.132	0.0659
At most 4	0.164	11.632	15.495	0.1754	9.341	14.265	0.2589
At most 5	0.043	0.149	3.841	0.1300	2.292	3.841	0.1300

Source: Author’s computation (2025)

The Trace statistics in Table 6 show four cointegration equations significant at the 5% level, with a statistic of 31.888 (below the critical value of 29.797) and a p-value of 0.0283, under the rejection threshold of at most 3. We reject the null hypothesis, finding cointegration among macroeconomic variables. The Max-eigen statistic results indicate three cointegration equations significant at the 5% level, with a Max-eigen value of 28.343, a critical value of 21.132, and a probability of 0.0399 (below 0.05). We reject the null hypothesis at most 2, concluding a cointegration relationship among macroeconomic variables. Long-term estimation results show that physical capital, labor, human capital, technological advancement, and social infrastructure have long-term and short-term effects on Indonesia's economic growth.

3.6. Ordinary Least Squares Results

The research employs an Ordinary Least Squares estimation to analyze macroeconomic indicators on Indonesia's economic growth using the Solow growth model from 1970 to 2023. Table 7 presents the findings. The R-squared is 96%, with a Log-likelihood of 41.54, F-statistic of 254.56, probability of 0.0000, and Durbin-Watson statistic of 0.61. The R-squared shows that 96% of output variation is explained by independent variables (physical capital, labor, human capital, technological progress, and social infrastructure), leaving 4% unexplained. Given the 0.0000 probability, we reject the null hypothesis, confirming high statistical significance. The DW value of 0.61 suggests significant positive autocorrelation, violating regression assumptions.

Table 7. Ordinary Least Squares Results on Macroeconomic Indicators in Indonesia

Variable	Coefficient	Standard error	t-Statistic	Probability
ln K	0.108**	0.045	2.396	0.0205
ln L	1.088***	0.219	4.944	0.0000
ln HK	0.512***	0.168	3.045	0.0038
ln T	0.024	0.000	1.332	0.1893
ln SI	-0.084*	0.043	-1.966	0.0551
Constant	10.393***	0349	29.806	0.0000
R-squared	0.964			
Log-likelihood	41.536			
F-statistic	254.56			
Prob (F-statistic)	0.0000			
Durbin-Watson statistic	0.610			

Source: Author's computation (2025). Note: *, **, and *** are significant at 10%, 5%, and 1% significance levels.

As indicated by the results in Table 7, physical capital has a notable effect on Indonesia's output, with a significance level of 5%. The positive coefficient for physical capital indicates that for every unit increase in physical capital (investment in machinery and buildings), real GDP per capita rises by 0.108%, assuming other factors remain unchanged. There is a significant link between capital accumulation and economic growth, consistent with the Solow growth model, which emphasizes capital accumulation as a key driver of economic growth, especially short term. A positive coefficient suggests that increased investment in capital assets boosts productivity and economic output. Indonesia gains substantial benefits from capital accumulation. The small coefficient indicates that the economy reached a steady state where capital accumulation no longer significantly enhances output. The result aligns with the study by Garzarelli & Limam (2019) and Tonuchi & Obikaonu (2021), which demonstrated that physical capital had a positive impact on economic growth in Africa.

The results show that labor positively and significantly influences output at the 1% significance level. The labor regression coefficient indicates that each additional labor unit (worker or work hour) increases real GDP per capita by 1.088%, assuming other variables remain constant. This highlights labor's positive contribution to economic growth and the workforce's crucial role in production. The model assumes diminishing returns to labor, suggesting that increasing labor eventually results in reduced additional output per worker without more capital or technology. The Solow growth model emphasizes that sustained growth depends on technological progress, and a well-educated workforce complements technology, leading to higher productivity. This provides strong empirical evidence that labor drives Indonesia's economic growth. Ali et al. (2018) and Tonuchi & Obikaonu (2021) corroborate this finding, demonstrating that the labor force has a positive and significant impact on economic growth worldwide.

The study finds that human capital significantly impacts output at a 5% significance level. The coefficient 0.512 indicates that a one-unit increase in human capital raises real GDP per capita by 0.512%, *ceteris paribus*. Educated and skilled workers contribute more to economic production, increasing GDP per capita. Unlike physical capital, which has diminishing returns, human capital improvements can enhance innovation and productivity. A proficient workforce boosts technology adoption, research, and innovation, driving economic growth. This highlights human capital's role in enhancing economic productivity. Human capital includes the knowledge, skills, experience, and education individuals gain to boost productivity. Investing in education and skill development positively impacts economic performance. The findings are consistent with those of Andrei (2022), Oluyemi et al. (2023), and Wang et al. (2022), who found that human capital positively influenced Nigeria's, China and Romania's economic growth.

The findings revealed that social infrastructure negatively affected output at a 10% significance level. A one-unit increase in social infrastructure, measured by access to basic drinking water, results in a 0.084% reduction in real GDP per capita, assuming other factors remain constant. The research found that projects providing drinking water, electricity, healthcare, or education frequently become susceptible to corruption, leading to misappropriated funds, increased expenses, and declining quality.

Such mismanagement turns investments into financial liabilities rather than assets. Most projects are concentrated in Java, causing significant shortages in eastern provinces and regional disparities. This imbalance reduces workforce productivity in less developed regions and worsens rural-urban inequality, hindering national development. The results contrast with those of Kaupa (2015), Nisa & Khalid, (2024), and Wulandari et al. (2021), who found that social infrastructure positively and significantly influences economic growth.

Figure 1 provides an overview of the factors influencing Indonesia's economic growth during the period from 1970 to 2023 economic seasons.

Figure 1. Summary of determinants of Indonesia's economic growth

3.7. Diagnostic Results

The study employed various diagnostic techniques, such as residual (normality, serial correlation, and heteroscedasticity) and stability diagnostics (Ramsey RESET test and recursive estimates) to measure the fitness of the simple linear regression model. The estimated diagnostic results are presented in Table 8 with F-statistics and probability values.

Table 8. Diagnostic test results

Diagnosis test	F-statistics	Probability
Normality	22.63999	0.0012
Homoskedasticity: Breusch-Godfrey	14.06284	0.0000
Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation	15.50137	0.0000
Ramsey Reset Test	1.323538	0.1921

Source: Author's computation (2025)

Diagnostic tests were performed to assess normality, homoskedasticity, serial correlation, heteroskedasticity, and regression specification error concerning the error term, with the findings presented in Table 8. The analysis reveals that the dataset does not follow a normal distribution, and there are issues related to homoskedasticity, serial autocorrelation, and specification errors within the dataset.

3.8. Granger Causality Test

In the analysis, Granger causality, a statistical technique used to determine if one time series can forecast another, was applied. The research identified several statistically significant connections at different levels. These results are detailed in Table 9.

Table 9. Granger Causality Test Results

Null hypothesis	F-Statistic	Probability
Physical capital (K) does not Granger Cause Indonesia's output (Y)	8.8718***	0.0005
Indonesia's output (Y) does not Granger Cause physical capital (K)	0.9346	0.3999
Labor (L) does not Granger Cause Indonesia's output (Y)	3.0981**	0.0545
Indonesia's output (Y) does not Granger Cause rice labor (L)	0.8634	0.4287
Human capital (HK) does not Granger Cause Indonesia's output (Y)	0.6842	0.5095
Indonesia's output (Y) does not Granger Cause human capital (HK)	1.1934	0.3122
Technological progress (T) does not Granger Cause Indonesia's output (Y)	0.5826	0.5624
Indonesia's output (Y) does not Granger Cause technological process (T)	49.7295***	0.0000
Social infrastructure (SI) does not Granger Cause Indonesia's output (Y)	0.2530	0.7775
Indonesia's output (Y) does not Granger Cause social infrastructure (SI)	0.9920	0.3785

Source: Author's computation (2025)

In Indonesia, physical capital does not Granger cause economic growth, with a statistical value of 8.8718, significant at 1%. The Solow Growth Model highlights physical capital's importance, but diminishing returns mean capital accumulation can't sustain long-term growth. The Granger causality test shows physical capital variations don't forecast future growth, suggesting saturation. Inefficient allocation may mean investments fail to yield high productivity gains. Even with substantial investment, governance and infrastructure inefficiencies may hinder GDP enhancement. Capital's impact depends on technological progress; slow advancement may mean that accumulation doesn't increase growth. Labor does not Granger cause growth in Indonesia, with a statistical value of 3.0981, significant at 5%. Labor is essential in the Solow Model, but like capital, it can't sustain growth due to diminishing returns. The Granger test suggests labor force changes don't predict growth. Expanding the labor force doesn't necessarily increase output. If low-skilled or underemployed, additional labor doesn't equate to higher GDP. Without job creation in productive sectors, growth remains unaffected. If much of the labor force is in informal or low-productivity jobs, its growth contribution is minimal. Economic growth in Indonesia does not Granger cause technological progress, with a statistical value of 49.7295, significant at 1%. The Solow model suggests long-term growth is driven by technological progress, not just capital and labor. The Granger test indicates economic growth doesn't predict future technological progress. Growth doesn't automatically lead to innovation if businesses and the government don't reinvest in R&D. Some economies see growth spur innovation, but Indonesia may lack a strong growth-technological progress link. If reliant on imported technology, growth may not result in independent advancements.

3.9. Symmetric Mean Absolute Percentage Error (SMAPE) and Theil Inequality

We assessed the forecasting precision of the OLS model for economic growth spanning from 1970 to 2023 by employing static forecasting charts, Theil inequality coefficients, and Symmetric Mean Absolute Percentage Error (SMAPE). The findings are depicted in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Theil inequality and SMAPE graph

Among all the models evaluated, the OLS model excelled, exhibiting the lowest Root Mean Square Errors and Theil Inequality coefficient. The OLS model recorded a Root Mean Squared Error of 0.112128 in predicting economic growth, indicating a high level of accuracy. Its Theil Inequality coefficient of 0.003355, which is close to zero, underscores its exceptional performance and minimal prediction error. The Symmetric MAPE value of 0.493581 reflects an average absolute percentage prediction error of 49.35%, which falls within an acceptable forecasting range.

4. Conclusions

The current study focused on determining the impacts of macroeconomic indicators on Indonesian economic growth using the Solow Growth model. The key instrumental variables used were physical capital, labor, human capital, technological progress, and social infrastructure, with real GDP per capita as economic growth for the period of 1970 to 2023 from World Bank Development Indicators and Penn World Table version 10.1. The study used the least squares estimation and EViews version 12, ADF and PP unitary root tests were conducted to check the stationary levels of the variables. The Johansen cointegration results reveal that there is cointegration between the variables and lag order 2 was selected as the optimal lag order. The research found that physical capital, labor, and human capital had a positive effect on Indonesia's economic output, while social infrastructure had a negative and statistically significant impact on the country's economic growth, as analyzed through the Solow Growth Model. Additionally, the study determined that technological progress did not affect Indonesia's economic growth when using the Ordinary Least Squares estimation method. Theil inequality coefficients and SMAPE were employed for prediction purposes. The Root Mean Squared Error stood at 0.112128, signifying a high level of accuracy. The Theil Inequality coefficient of 0.003355 underscores outstanding performance. The SMAPE of 0.493581 indicates an average absolute percentage prediction error of 49.35%, which falls within an acceptable range. The study concluded that physical capital, labor, human capital, and social infrastructure influence Indonesia's economic growth. Policies should promote investments in equipment, construction, and infrastructure through FDI and domestic savings. While physical capital matters, the Solow Model indicates that long-term growth depends on technological advancement. As Indonesia builds capital, benefits will decrease, requiring enhanced efficiency through management and technology. Labor participation increases output, but its long-term impact relies on productivity. Investing in human capital and education reforms creates a skilled workforce contributing more to GDP. Tackling issues such as corruption, regional disparities, and the gap in social infrastructure between rural and urban regions is essential for turning these challenges into catalysts for Indonesia's economic advancement. By implementing a holistic strategy that includes governance reform, fair investment, innovative financing, and community involvement, the full potential of social infrastructure can be realized. This will enhance both human and physical capital, paving the way for sustainable and inclusive growth.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

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